

1 **CLEC11A and CLEC2B mediate tumor surveillance through HLA-V and KIR2DL3.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We describe here a function of CLEC11A and CLEC2B in tumor surveillance through HLA-V and
8 KIR2DL3. HLA-V distinguished KIR2DL3+ cell fractions: Kir family receptors were induced or repressed
9 together with HLA-V. Slamf6 was silenced, as was FNDC3A. Both Clec11a and Clec2b were activated.
10 Other Clec family receptors were involved in tumor surveillance through HLA-V and KIR2DL3 including
11 C-type lectin receptors of the Clec18 family and Clec4A. Fam43A and Ano9 marked these cells, together
12 with NCR3. Fam223A/B expression was shared, as was Fam226A/B, Fam247C/D, Gpr34 and Gpr82.
13 Clec11a and Clec2b signaling involved the functions of Icoslg and LILR receptors LILRA1/2 and LILRB2/3.
14 Lymphocyte antigen family receptors were, consistent with previous description of HLA-V function,
15 important for Clec11a and Clec2b signaling; Ly9 was modestly induced in KIR2DL3hi cells while Ly6E was
16 expressed in large quantity but not significantly different in KIR2DL3(hi) and KIR2DL3(lo) cells. Thus,
17 CLEC11A and CLEC2B function as co-receptors in tumor surveillance through HLA-V and KIR2DL3.
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